

The Royal Society (U.K.) - License Terms and Conditions

This is a License Agreement between Achmed Mrestani ("You") and The Royal Society (U.K.) ("Publisher") provided by Copyright Clearance Center ("CCC"). The license consists of your order details, the terms and conditions provided by The Royal Society (U.K.), and the CCC terms and conditions.

All payments must be made in full to CCC.

Order Date	10-Nov-2020	Type of Use	Republish in a thesis/dissertation
Order license ID	1076514-1	Publisher Portion	Royal Society of London Image/photo/illustration
ISSN	2053-9169		

LICENSED CONTENT

Publication Title	Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series A, Mathematical and physical sciences	Country	United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland
Author/Editor	Royal Society (Great Britain)	Rightsholder	The Royal Society (U.K.)
Date	01/01/1934	Publication Type	e-Journal
Language	English	URL	https://royalsociety.org/journals/

REQUEST DETAILS

Portion Type	Image/photo/illustration	Distribution	Worldwide
Number of images / photos / illustrations	1	Translation	Original language of publication
Format (select all that apply)	Print, Electronic	Copies for the disabled?	No
Who will republish the content?	Academic institution	Minor editing privileges?	Yes
Duration of Use	Life of current and all future editions	Incidental promotional use?	No
Lifetime Unit Quantity	Up to 499	Currency	EUR
Rights Requested	Main product		

NEW WORK DETAILS

Title	Strukturelle Differenzierung und Plastizität präsynaptischer Aktiver Zonen	Institution name	University of Würzburg
Instructor name	Achmed Mrestani	Expected presentation date	2021-11-01

ADDITIONAL DETAILS

Order reference number	katz1965b	The requesting person / organization to appear on the license	Achmed Mrestani
------------------------	-----------	---	-----------------

REUSE CONTENT DETAILS

Title, description or numeric reference of the portion(s)	Figure 1	Title of the article/chapter the portion is from	The measurement of synaptic delay, and the time course of acetylcholine release at the neuromuscular junction
Editor of portion(s)	N/A	Author of portion(s)	Royal Society (Great Britain)
Volume of serial or monograph	Volume 161	Issue, if republishing an article from a serial	N/A
Page or page range of portion	484	Publication date of portion	1965-02-16

PUBLISHER TERMS AND CONDITIONS

Out of Copyright - any journal requested with a Publication date older than 70 years.

CCC Republication Terms and Conditions

1. Description of Service; Defined Terms. This Republication License enables the User to obtain licenses for republication of one or more copyrighted works as described in detail on the relevant Order Confirmation (the "Work(s)"). Copyright Clearance Center, Inc. ("CCC") grants licenses through the Service on behalf of the rightsholder identified on the Order Confirmation (the "Rightsholder"). "Republication", as used herein, generally means the inclusion of a Work, in whole or in part, in a new work or works, also as described on the Order Confirmation. "User", as used herein, means the person or entity making such republication.
2. The terms set forth in the relevant Order Confirmation, and any terms set by the Rightsholder with respect to a particular Work, govern the terms of use of Works in connection with the Service. By using the Service, the person transacting for a republication license on behalf of the User represents and warrants that he/she/it (a) has been duly authorized by the User to accept, and hereby does accept, all such terms and conditions on behalf of User, and (b) shall inform User of all such terms and conditions. In the event such person is a "freelancer" or other third party independent of User and CCC, such party shall be deemed jointly a "User" for purposes of these terms and conditions. In any event, User shall be deemed to have accepted and agreed to all such terms and conditions if User republishes the Work in any fashion.
3. Scope of License; Limitations and Obligations.
 - 3.1. All Works and all rights therein, including copyright rights, remain the sole and exclusive property of the Rightsholder. The license created by the exchange of an Order Confirmation (and/or any invoice) and payment by User of the full amount set forth on that document includes only those rights expressly set forth in the Order Confirmation and in these terms and conditions, and conveys no other rights in the Work(s) to User. All rights not expressly granted are hereby reserved.
 - 3.2. General Payment Terms: You may pay by credit card or through an account with us payable at the end of the month. If you and we agree that you may establish a standing account with CCC, then the following terms apply: Remit Payment to: Copyright Clearance Center, 29118 Network Place, Chicago, IL 60673-1291. Payments Due: Invoices are payable upon their delivery to you (or upon our notice to you that they are available to you for downloading). After 30 days, outstanding amounts will be subject to a service charge of 1-1/2% per month or, if less, the maximum rate allowed by applicable law. Unless otherwise specifically

set forth in the Order Confirmation or in a separate written agreement signed by CCC, invoices are due and payable on "net 30" terms. While User may exercise the rights licensed immediately upon issuance of the Order Confirmation, the license is automatically revoked and is null and void, as if it had never been issued, if complete payment for the license is not received on a timely basis either from User directly or through a payment agent, such as a credit card company.

- 3.3. Unless otherwise provided in the Order Confirmation, any grant of rights to User (i) is "one-time" (including the editions and product family specified in the license), (ii) is non-exclusive and non-transferable and (iii) is subject to any and all limitations and restrictions (such as, but not limited to, limitations on duration of use or circulation) included in the Order Confirmation or invoice and/or in these terms and conditions. Upon completion of the licensed use, User shall either secure a new permission for further use of the Work(s) or immediately cease any new use of the Work(s) and shall render inaccessible (such as by deleting or by removing or severing links or other locators) any further copies of the Work (except for copies printed on paper in accordance with this license and still in User's stock at the end of such period).
- 3.4. In the event that the material for which a republication license is sought includes third party materials (such as photographs, illustrations, graphs, inserts and similar materials) which are identified in such material as having been used by permission, User is responsible for identifying, and seeking separate licenses (under this Service or otherwise) for, any of such third party materials; without a separate license, such third party materials may not be used.
- 3.5. Use of proper copyright notice for a Work is required as a condition of any license granted under the Service. Unless otherwise provided in the Order Confirmation, a proper copyright notice will read substantially as follows: "Republished with permission of [Rightsholder's name], from [Work's title, author, volume, edition number and year of copyright]; permission conveyed through Copyright Clearance Center, Inc. " Such notice must be provided in a reasonably legible font size and must be placed either immediately adjacent to the Work as used (for example, as part of a by-line or footnote but not as a separate electronic link) or in the place where substantially all other credits or notices for the new work containing the republished Work are located. Failure to include the required notice results in loss to the Rightsholder and CCC, and the User shall be liable to pay liquidated damages for each such failure equal to twice the use fee specified in the Order Confirmation, in addition to the use fee itself and any other fees and charges specified.
- 3.6. User may only make alterations to the Work if and as expressly set forth in the Order Confirmation. No Work may be used in any way that is defamatory, violates the rights of third parties (including such third parties' rights of copyright, privacy, publicity, or other tangible or intangible property), or is otherwise illegal, sexually explicit or obscene. In addition, User may not conjoin a Work with any other material that may result in damage to the reputation of the Rightsholder. User agrees to inform CCC if it becomes aware of any infringement of any rights in a Work and to cooperate with any reasonable request of CCC or the Rightsholder in connection therewith.
4. Indemnity. User hereby indemnifies and agrees to defend the Rightsholder and CCC, and their respective employees and directors, against all claims, liability, damages, costs and expenses, including legal fees and expenses, arising out of any use of a Work beyond the scope of the rights granted herein, or any use of a Work which has been altered in any unauthorized way by User, including claims of defamation or infringement of rights of copyright, publicity, privacy or other tangible or intangible property.
5. Limitation of Liability. UNDER NO CIRCUMSTANCES WILL CCC OR THE RIGHTSHOLDER BE LIABLE FOR ANY DIRECT, INDIRECT, CONSEQUENTIAL OR INCIDENTAL DAMAGES (INCLUDING WITHOUT LIMITATION DAMAGES FOR LOSS OF BUSINESS PROFITS OR INFORMATION, OR FOR BUSINESS INTERRUPTION) ARISING OUT OF THE USE OR INABILITY TO USE A WORK, EVEN IF ONE OF THEM HAS BEEN ADVISED OF THE POSSIBILITY OF SUCH DAMAGES. In any event, the total liability of the Rightsholder and CCC (including their respective employees and directors) shall not exceed the total amount actually paid by User for this license. User assumes full liability for the actions and omissions of its principals, employees, agents, affiliates, successors and assigns.
- 6.

Limited Warranties. THE WORK(S) AND RIGHT(S) ARE PROVIDED "AS IS". CCC HAS THE RIGHT TO GRANT TO USER THE RIGHTS GRANTED IN THE ORDER CONFIRMATION DOCUMENT. CCC AND THE RIGHTSHOLDER DISCLAIM ALL OTHER WARRANTIES RELATING TO THE WORK(S) AND RIGHT(S), EITHER EXPRESS OR IMPLIED, INCLUDING WITHOUT LIMITATION IMPLIED WARRANTIES OF MERCHANTABILITY OR FITNESS FOR A PARTICULAR PURPOSE. ADDITIONAL RIGHTS MAY BE REQUIRED TO USE ILLUSTRATIONS, GRAPHS, PHOTOGRAPHS, ABSTRACTS, INSERTS OR OTHER PORTIONS OF THE WORK (AS OPPOSED TO THE ENTIRE WORK) IN A MANNER CONTEMPLATED BY USER; USER UNDERSTANDS AND AGREES THAT NEITHER CCC NOR THE RIGHTSHOLDER MAY HAVE SUCH ADDITIONAL RIGHTS TO GRANT.

7. Effect of Breach. Any failure by User to pay any amount when due, or any use by User of a Work beyond the scope of the license set forth in the Order Confirmation and/or these terms and conditions, shall be a material breach of the license created by the Order Confirmation and these terms and conditions. Any breach not cured within 30 days of written notice thereof shall result in immediate termination of such license without further notice. Any unauthorized (but licensable) use of a Work that is terminated immediately upon notice thereof may be liquidated by payment of the Rightsholder's ordinary license price therefor; any unauthorized (and unlicensable) use that is not terminated immediately for any reason (including, for example, because materials containing the Work cannot reasonably be recalled) will be subject to all remedies available at law or in equity, but in no event to a payment of less than three times the Rightsholder's ordinary license price for the most closely analogous licensable use plus Rightsholder's and/or CCC's costs and expenses incurred in collecting such payment.

8. Miscellaneous.

8.1. User acknowledges that CCC may, from time to time, make changes or additions to the Service or to these terms and conditions, and CCC reserves the right to send notice to the User by electronic mail or otherwise for the purposes of notifying User of such changes or additions; provided that any such changes or additions shall not apply to permissions already secured and paid for.

8.2. Use of User-related information collected through the Service is governed by CCC's privacy policy, available online here:<https://marketplace.copyright.com/rs-ui-web/mp/privacy-policy>

8.3. The licensing transaction described in the Order Confirmation is personal to User. Therefore, User may not assign or transfer to any other person (whether a natural person or an organization of any kind) the license created by the Order Confirmation and these terms and conditions or any rights granted hereunder; provided, however, that User may assign such license in its entirety on written notice to CCC in the event of a transfer of all or substantially all of User's rights in the new material which includes the Work(s) licensed under this Service.

8.4. No amendment or waiver of any terms is binding unless set forth in writing and signed by the parties. The Rightsholder and CCC hereby object to any terms contained in any writing prepared by the User or its principals, employees, agents or affiliates and purporting to govern or otherwise relate to the licensing transaction described in the Order Confirmation, which terms are in any way inconsistent with any terms set forth in the Order Confirmation and/or in these terms and conditions or CCC's standard operating procedures, whether such writing is prepared prior to, simultaneously with or subsequent to the Order Confirmation, and whether such writing appears on a copy of the Order Confirmation or in a separate instrument.

8.5. The licensing transaction described in the Order Confirmation document shall be governed by and construed under the law of the State of New York, USA, without regard to the principles thereof of conflicts of law. Any case, controversy, suit, action, or proceeding arising out of, in connection with, or related to such licensing transaction shall be brought, at CCC's sole discretion, in any federal or state court located in the County of New York, State of New York, USA, or in any federal or state court whose geographical jurisdiction covers the location of the Rightsholder set forth in the Order Confirmation. The parties expressly submit to the personal jurisdiction and venue of each such federal or state court. If you have any comments or questions about the Service or Copyright Clearance Center, please contact us at 978-750-8400 or send an e-mail to support@copyright.com.

ELSEVIER LICENSE
TERMS AND CONDITIONS

Nov 08, 2020

This Agreement between Mr. Achmed Mrestani ("You") and Elsevier ("Elsevier") consists of your license details and the terms and conditions provided by Elsevier and Copyright Clearance Center.

License Number 4944180740945

License date Nov 08, 2020

Licensed Content Publisher Elsevier

Licensed Content
Publication Neuron

Licensed Content Title Genetic Analysis of Glutamate Receptors in Drosophila Reveals a Retrograde Signal Regulating Presynaptic Transmitter Release

Licensed Content Author Sophie A Petersen, Richard D Fetter, Jasprina N Noordermeer, Corey S Goodman, Aaron DiAntonio

Licensed Content Date Dec 1, 1997

Licensed Content Volume 19

Licensed Content Issue 6

Licensed Content Pages 12

Start Page 1237

End Page 1248

Type of Use	reuse in a thesis/dissertation
Portion	figures/tables/illustrations
Number of figures/tables /illustrations	1
Format	both print and electronic
Are you the author of this Elsevier article?	No
Will you be translating?	No
Title	Strukturelle Differenzierung und Plastizität präsynaptischer Aktiver Zonen
Institution name	University of Würzburg
Expected presentation date	Jan 2021
Order reference number	petersen1997
Portions	Figure 4
Requestor Location	Mr. Achmed Mrestani Geiststraße 23 Halle, Sachsen-Anhalt 06108 Germany Attn: Mr. Achmed Mrestani
Publisher Tax ID	GB 494 6272 12
Total	0.00 EUR
Terms and Conditions	

INTRODUCTION

1. The publisher for this copyrighted material is Elsevier. By clicking "accept" in connection with completing this licensing transaction, you agree that the following terms and conditions apply to this transaction (along with the Billing and Payment terms and conditions established by Copyright Clearance Center, Inc. ("CCC"), at the time that you opened your Rightslink account and that are available at any time at <http://myaccount.copyright.com>).

GENERAL TERMS

2. Elsevier hereby grants you permission to reproduce the aforementioned material subject to the terms and conditions indicated.

3. Acknowledgement: If any part of the material to be used (for example, figures) has appeared in our publication with credit or acknowledgement to another source, permission must also be sought from that source. If such permission is not obtained then that material may not be included in your publication/copies. Suitable acknowledgement to the source must be made, either as a footnote or in a reference list at the end of your publication, as follows:

"Reprinted from Publication title, Vol /edition number, Author(s), Title of article / title of chapter, Pages No., Copyright (Year), with permission from Elsevier [OR APPLICABLE SOCIETY COPYRIGHT OWNER]." Also Lancet special credit - "Reprinted from The Lancet, Vol. number, Author(s), Title of article, Pages No., Copyright (Year), with permission from Elsevier."

4. Reproduction of this material is confined to the purpose and/or media for which permission is hereby given.

5. Altering/Modifying Material: Not Permitted. However figures and illustrations may be altered/adapted minimally to serve your work. Any other abbreviations, additions, deletions and/or any other alterations shall be made only with prior written authorization of Elsevier Ltd. (Please contact Elsevier's permissions helpdesk [here](#)). No modifications can be made to any Lancet figures/tables and they must be reproduced in full.

6. If the permission fee for the requested use of our material is waived in this instance, please be advised that your future requests for Elsevier materials may attract a fee.

7. Reservation of Rights: Publisher reserves all rights not specifically granted in the combination of (i) the license details provided by you and accepted in the course of this licensing transaction, (ii) these terms and conditions and (iii) CCC's Billing and Payment terms and conditions.

8. License Contingent Upon Payment: While you may exercise the rights licensed immediately upon issuance of the license at the end of the licensing process for the transaction, provided that you have disclosed complete and accurate details of your proposed use, no license is finally effective unless and until full payment is received from you (either by publisher or by CCC) as provided in CCC's Billing and Payment terms and conditions. If full payment is not received on a timely basis, then any license preliminarily granted shall be deemed automatically revoked and shall be void as if never granted. Further, in the event that you breach any of these terms and conditions or any of CCC's Billing and Payment terms and conditions, the license is automatically revoked and shall be void as if never granted. Use of materials as described in a revoked license, as well as any use of the materials beyond the scope of an unrevoked license, may constitute copyright infringement

and publisher reserves the right to take any and all action to protect its copyright in the materials.

9. **Warranties:** Publisher makes no representations or warranties with respect to the licensed material.

10. **Indemnity:** You hereby indemnify and agree to hold harmless publisher and CCC, and their respective officers, directors, employees and agents, from and against any and all claims arising out of your use of the licensed material other than as specifically authorized pursuant to this license.

11. **No Transfer of License:** This license is personal to you and may not be sublicensed, assigned, or transferred by you to any other person without publisher's written permission.

12. **No Amendment Except in Writing:** This license may not be amended except in a writing signed by both parties (or, in the case of publisher, by CCC on publisher's behalf).

13. **Objection to Contrary Terms:** Publisher hereby objects to any terms contained in any purchase order, acknowledgment, check endorsement or other writing prepared by you, which terms are inconsistent with these terms and conditions or CCC's Billing and Payment terms and conditions. These terms and conditions, together with CCC's Billing and Payment terms and conditions (which are incorporated herein), comprise the entire agreement between you and publisher (and CCC) concerning this licensing transaction. In the event of any conflict between your obligations established by these terms and conditions and those established by CCC's Billing and Payment terms and conditions, these terms and conditions shall control.

14. **Revocation:** Elsevier or Copyright Clearance Center may deny the permissions described in this License at their sole discretion, for any reason or no reason, with a full refund payable to you. Notice of such denial will be made using the contact information provided by you. Failure to receive such notice will not alter or invalidate the denial. In no event will Elsevier or Copyright Clearance Center be responsible or liable for any costs, expenses or damage incurred by you as a result of a denial of your permission request, other than a refund of the amount(s) paid by you to Elsevier and/or Copyright Clearance Center for denied permissions.

LIMITED LICENSE

The following terms and conditions apply only to specific license types:

15. **Translation:** This permission is granted for non-exclusive world **English** rights only unless your license was granted for translation rights. If you licensed translation rights you may only translate this content into the languages you requested. A professional translator must perform all translations and reproduce the content word for word preserving the integrity of the article.

16. **Posting licensed content on any Website:** The following terms and conditions apply as follows: Licensing material from an Elsevier journal: All content posted to the web site must maintain the copyright information line on the bottom of each image; A hyper-text must be included to the Homepage of the journal from which you are licensing at <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/journal/xxxxx> or the Elsevier homepage for books at <http://www.elsevier.com>; Central Storage: This license does not include permission for a scanned version of the material to be stored in a central repository such as that provided by Heron/XanEdu.

Licensing material from an Elsevier book: A hyper-text link must be included to the Elsevier

homepage at <http://www.elsevier.com> . All content posted to the web site must maintain the copyright information line on the bottom of each image.

Posting licensed content on Electronic reserve: In addition to the above the following clauses are applicable: The web site must be password-protected and made available only to bona fide students registered on a relevant course. This permission is granted for 1 year only. You may obtain a new license for future website posting.

17. **For journal authors:** the following clauses are applicable in addition to the above:

Preprints:

A preprint is an author's own write-up of research results and analysis, it has not been peer-reviewed, nor has it had any other value added to it by a publisher (such as formatting, copyright, technical enhancement etc.).

Authors can share their preprints anywhere at any time. Preprints should not be added to or enhanced in any way in order to appear more like, or to substitute for, the final versions of articles however authors can update their preprints on arXiv or RePEc with their Accepted Author Manuscript (see below).

If accepted for publication, we encourage authors to link from the preprint to their formal publication via its DOI. Millions of researchers have access to the formal publications on ScienceDirect, and so links will help users to find, access, cite and use the best available version. Please note that Cell Press, The Lancet and some society-owned have different preprint policies. Information on these policies is available on the journal homepage.

Accepted Author Manuscripts: An accepted author manuscript is the manuscript of an article that has been accepted for publication and which typically includes author-incorporated changes suggested during submission, peer review and editor-author communications.

Authors can share their accepted author manuscript:

- immediately
 - via their non-commercial person homepage or blog
 - by updating a preprint in arXiv or RePEc with the accepted manuscript
 - via their research institute or institutional repository for internal institutional uses or as part of an invitation-only research collaboration work-group
 - directly by providing copies to their students or to research collaborators for their personal use
 - for private scholarly sharing as part of an invitation-only work group on commercial sites with which Elsevier has an agreement
- After the embargo period
 - via non-commercial hosting platforms such as their institutional repository
 - via commercial sites with which Elsevier has an agreement

In all cases accepted manuscripts should:

- link to the formal publication via its DOI
- bear a CC-BY-NC-ND license - this is easy to do
- if aggregated with other manuscripts, for example in a repository or other site, be shared in alignment with our hosting policy not be added to or enhanced in any way to appear more like, or to substitute for, the published journal article.

Published journal article (JPA): A published journal article (PJA) is the definitive final record of published research that appears or will appear in the journal and embodies all value-adding publishing activities including peer review co-ordination, copy-editing, formatting, (if relevant) pagination and online enrichment.

Policies for sharing publishing journal articles differ for subscription and gold open access articles:

Subscription Articles: If you are an author, please share a link to your article rather than the full-text. Millions of researchers have access to the formal publications on ScienceDirect, and so links will help your users to find, access, cite, and use the best available version.

Theses and dissertations which contain embedded PJAs as part of the formal submission can be posted publicly by the awarding institution with DOI links back to the formal publications on ScienceDirect.

If you are affiliated with a library that subscribes to ScienceDirect you have additional private sharing rights for others' research accessed under that agreement. This includes use for classroom teaching and internal training at the institution (including use in course packs and courseware programs), and inclusion of the article for grant funding purposes.

Gold Open Access Articles: May be shared according to the author-selected end-user license and should contain a [CrossMark logo](#), the end user license, and a DOI link to the formal publication on ScienceDirect.

Please refer to Elsevier's [posting policy](#) for further information.

18. **For book authors** the following clauses are applicable in addition to the above: Authors are permitted to place a brief summary of their work online only. You are not allowed to download and post the published electronic version of your chapter, nor may you scan the printed edition to create an electronic version. **Posting to a repository:** Authors are permitted to post a summary of their chapter only in their institution's repository.

19. **Thesis/Dissertation:** If your license is for use in a thesis/dissertation your thesis may be submitted to your institution in either print or electronic form. Should your thesis be published commercially, please reapply for permission. These requirements include permission for the Library and Archives of Canada to supply single copies, on demand, of the complete thesis and include permission for Proquest/UMI to supply single copies, on demand, of the complete thesis. Should your thesis be published commercially, please reapply for permission. Theses and dissertations which contain embedded PJAs as part of the formal submission can be posted publicly by the awarding institution with DOI links back to the formal publications on ScienceDirect.

Elsevier Open Access Terms and Conditions

You can publish open access with Elsevier in hundreds of open access journals or in nearly 2000 established subscription journals that support open access publishing. Permitted third party re-use of these open access articles is defined by the author's choice of Creative Commons user license. See our [open access license policy](#) for more information.

Terms & Conditions applicable to all Open Access articles published with Elsevier:

Any reuse of the article must not represent the author as endorsing the adaptation of the

article nor should the article be modified in such a way as to damage the author's honour or reputation. If any changes have been made, such changes must be clearly indicated.

The author(s) must be appropriately credited and we ask that you include the end user license and a DOI link to the formal publication on ScienceDirect.

If any part of the material to be used (for example, figures) has appeared in our publication with credit or acknowledgement to another source it is the responsibility of the user to ensure their reuse complies with the terms and conditions determined by the rights holder.

Additional Terms & Conditions applicable to each Creative Commons user license:

CC BY: The CC-BY license allows users to copy, to create extracts, abstracts and new works from the Article, to alter and revise the Article and to make commercial use of the Article (including reuse and/or resale of the Article by commercial entities), provided the user gives appropriate credit (with a link to the formal publication through the relevant DOI), provides a link to the license, indicates if changes were made and the licensor is not represented as endorsing the use made of the work. The full details of the license are available at <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>.

CC BY NC SA: The CC BY-NC-SA license allows users to copy, to create extracts, abstracts and new works from the Article, to alter and revise the Article, provided this is not done for commercial purposes, and that the user gives appropriate credit (with a link to the formal publication through the relevant DOI), provides a link to the license, indicates if changes were made and the licensor is not represented as endorsing the use made of the work. Further, any new works must be made available on the same conditions. The full details of the license are available at <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/4.0>.

CC BY NC ND: The CC BY-NC-ND license allows users to copy and distribute the Article, provided this is not done for commercial purposes and further does not permit distribution of the Article if it is changed or edited in any way, and provided the user gives appropriate credit (with a link to the formal publication through the relevant DOI), provides a link to the license, and that the licensor is not represented as endorsing the use made of the work. The full details of the license are available at <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-nd/4.0>. Any commercial reuse of Open Access articles published with a CC BY NC SA or CC BY NC ND license requires permission from Elsevier and will be subject to a fee.

Commercial reuse includes:

- Associating advertising with the full text of the Article
- Charging fees for document delivery or access
- Article aggregation
- Systematic distribution via e-mail lists or share buttons

Posting or linking by commercial companies for use by customers of those companies.

20. Other Conditions:

v1.10

Questions? customercare@copyright.com or +1-855-239-3415 (toll free in the US) or +1-978-646-2777.

ELSEVIER LICENSE
TERMS AND CONDITIONS

Nov 08, 2020

This Agreement between Mr. Achmed Mrestani ("You") and Elsevier ("Elsevier") consists of your license details and the terms and conditions provided by Elsevier and Copyright Clearance Center.

License Number	4944180240341
License date	Nov 08, 2020
Licensed Content Publisher	Elsevier
Licensed Content Publication	Neuron
Licensed Content Title	Mechanisms Underlying the Rapid Induction and Sustained Expression of Synaptic Homeostasis
Licensed Content Author	C. Andrew Frank,Matthew J. Kennedy,Carleton P. Goold,Kurt W. Marek,Graeme W. Davis
Licensed Content Date	Nov 22, 2006
Licensed Content Volume	52
Licensed Content Issue	4
Licensed Content Pages	15
Start Page	663
End Page	677
Type of Use	reuse in a thesis/dissertation

Portion	figures/tables/illustrations
Number of figures/tables /illustrations	1
Format	both print and electronic
Are you the author of this Elsevier article?	No
Will you be translating?	No
Title	Strukturelle Differenzierung und Plastizität präsynaptischer Aktiver Zonen
Institution name	University of Würzburg
Expected presentation date	Jan 2021
Order reference number	frank2006
Portions	Figure 2
Requestor Location	Mr. Achmed Mrestani Geiststraße 23 Halle, Sachsen-Anhalt 06108 Germany Attn: Mr. Achmed Mrestani
Publisher Tax ID	GB 494 6272 12
Total	0.00 EUR
Terms and Conditions	

INTRODUCTION

1. The publisher for this copyrighted material is Elsevier. By clicking "accept" in connection with completing this licensing transaction, you agree that the following terms

and conditions apply to this transaction (along with the Billing and Payment terms and conditions established by Copyright Clearance Center, Inc. ("CCC"), at the time that you opened your Rightslink account and that are available at any time at <http://myaccount.copyright.com>).

GENERAL TERMS

2. Elsevier hereby grants you permission to reproduce the aforementioned material subject to the terms and conditions indicated.

3. Acknowledgement: If any part of the material to be used (for example, figures) has appeared in our publication with credit or acknowledgement to another source, permission must also be sought from that source. If such permission is not obtained then that material may not be included in your publication/copies. Suitable acknowledgement to the source must be made, either as a footnote or in a reference list at the end of your publication, as follows:

"Reprinted from Publication title, Vol /edition number, Author(s), Title of article / title of chapter, Pages No., Copyright (Year), with permission from Elsevier [OR APPLICABLE SOCIETY COPYRIGHT OWNER]." Also Lancet special credit - "Reprinted from The Lancet, Vol. number, Author(s), Title of article, Pages No., Copyright (Year), with permission from Elsevier."

4. Reproduction of this material is confined to the purpose and/or media for which permission is hereby given.

5. Altering/Modifying Material: Not Permitted. However figures and illustrations may be altered/adapted minimally to serve your work. Any other abbreviations, additions, deletions and/or any other alterations shall be made only with prior written authorization of Elsevier Ltd. (Please contact Elsevier's permissions helpdesk [here](#)). No modifications can be made to any Lancet figures/tables and they must be reproduced in full.

6. If the permission fee for the requested use of our material is waived in this instance, please be advised that your future requests for Elsevier materials may attract a fee.

7. Reservation of Rights: Publisher reserves all rights not specifically granted in the combination of (i) the license details provided by you and accepted in the course of this licensing transaction, (ii) these terms and conditions and (iii) CCC's Billing and Payment terms and conditions.

8. License Contingent Upon Payment: While you may exercise the rights licensed immediately upon issuance of the license at the end of the licensing process for the transaction, provided that you have disclosed complete and accurate details of your proposed use, no license is finally effective unless and until full payment is received from you (either by publisher or by CCC) as provided in CCC's Billing and Payment terms and conditions. If full payment is not received on a timely basis, then any license preliminarily granted shall be deemed automatically revoked and shall be void as if never granted. Further, in the event that you breach any of these terms and conditions or any of CCC's Billing and Payment terms and conditions, the license is automatically revoked and shall be void as if never granted. Use of materials as described in a revoked license, as well as any use of the materials beyond the scope of an unrevoked license, may constitute copyright infringement and publisher reserves the right to take any and all action to protect its copyright in the materials.

9. Warranties: Publisher makes no representations or warranties with respect to the licensed material.

10. **Indemnity:** You hereby indemnify and agree to hold harmless publisher and CCC, and their respective officers, directors, employees and agents, from and against any and all claims arising out of your use of the licensed material other than as specifically authorized pursuant to this license.

11. **No Transfer of License:** This license is personal to you and may not be sublicensed, assigned, or transferred by you to any other person without publisher's written permission.

12. **No Amendment Except in Writing:** This license may not be amended except in a writing signed by both parties (or, in the case of publisher, by CCC on publisher's behalf).

13. **Objection to Contrary Terms:** Publisher hereby objects to any terms contained in any purchase order, acknowledgment, check endorsement or other writing prepared by you, which terms are inconsistent with these terms and conditions or CCC's Billing and Payment terms and conditions. These terms and conditions, together with CCC's Billing and Payment terms and conditions (which are incorporated herein), comprise the entire agreement between you and publisher (and CCC) concerning this licensing transaction. In the event of any conflict between your obligations established by these terms and conditions and those established by CCC's Billing and Payment terms and conditions, these terms and conditions shall control.

14. **Revocation:** Elsevier or Copyright Clearance Center may deny the permissions described in this License at their sole discretion, for any reason or no reason, with a full refund payable to you. Notice of such denial will be made using the contact information provided by you. Failure to receive such notice will not alter or invalidate the denial. In no event will Elsevier or Copyright Clearance Center be responsible or liable for any costs, expenses or damage incurred by you as a result of a denial of your permission request, other than a refund of the amount(s) paid by you to Elsevier and/or Copyright Clearance Center for denied permissions.

LIMITED LICENSE

The following terms and conditions apply only to specific license types:

15. **Translation:** This permission is granted for non-exclusive world **English** rights only unless your license was granted for translation rights. If you licensed translation rights you may only translate this content into the languages you requested. A professional translator must perform all translations and reproduce the content word for word preserving the integrity of the article.

16. **Posting licensed content on any Website:** The following terms and conditions apply as follows: Licensing material from an Elsevier journal: All content posted to the web site must maintain the copyright information line on the bottom of each image; A hyper-text must be included to the Homepage of the journal from which you are licensing at <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/journal/xxxxx> or the Elsevier homepage for books at <http://www.elsevier.com>; Central Storage: This license does not include permission for a scanned version of the material to be stored in a central repository such as that provided by Heron/XanEdu.

Licensing material from an Elsevier book: A hyper-text link must be included to the Elsevier homepage at <http://www.elsevier.com>. All content posted to the web site must maintain the copyright information line on the bottom of each image.

Posting licensed content on Electronic reserve: In addition to the above the following

clauses are applicable: The web site must be password-protected and made available only to bona fide students registered on a relevant course. This permission is granted for 1 year only. You may obtain a new license for future website posting.

17. For journal authors: the following clauses are applicable in addition to the above:

Preprints:

A preprint is an author's own write-up of research results and analysis, it has not been peer-reviewed, nor has it had any other value added to it by a publisher (such as formatting, copyright, technical enhancement etc.).

Authors can share their preprints anywhere at any time. Preprints should not be added to or enhanced in any way in order to appear more like, or to substitute for, the final versions of articles however authors can update their preprints on arXiv or RePEc with their Accepted Author Manuscript (see below).

If accepted for publication, we encourage authors to link from the preprint to their formal publication via its DOI. Millions of researchers have access to the formal publications on ScienceDirect, and so links will help users to find, access, cite and use the best available version. Please note that Cell Press, The Lancet and some society-owned have different preprint policies. Information on these policies is available on the journal homepage.

Accepted Author Manuscripts: An accepted author manuscript is the manuscript of an article that has been accepted for publication and which typically includes author-incorporated changes suggested during submission, peer review and editor-author communications.

Authors can share their accepted author manuscript:

- immediately
 - via their non-commercial person homepage or blog
 - by updating a preprint in arXiv or RePEc with the accepted manuscript
 - via their research institute or institutional repository for internal institutional uses or as part of an invitation-only research collaboration work-group
 - directly by providing copies to their students or to research collaborators for their personal use
 - for private scholarly sharing as part of an invitation-only work group on commercial sites with which Elsevier has an agreement
- After the embargo period
 - via non-commercial hosting platforms such as their institutional repository
 - via commercial sites with which Elsevier has an agreement

In all cases accepted manuscripts should:

- link to the formal publication via its DOI
- bear a CC-BY-NC-ND license - this is easy to do
- if aggregated with other manuscripts, for example in a repository or other site, be shared in alignment with our hosting policy not be added to or enhanced in any way to appear more like, or to substitute for, the published journal article.

Published journal article (JPA): A published journal article (PJA) is the definitive final record of published research that appears or will appear in the journal and embodies all value-adding publishing activities including peer review co-ordination, copy-editing, formatting, (if relevant) pagination and online enrichment.

Policies for sharing publishing journal articles differ for subscription and gold open access articles:

Subscription Articles: If you are an author, please share a link to your article rather than the full-text. Millions of researchers have access to the formal publications on ScienceDirect, and so links will help your users to find, access, cite, and use the best available version.

Theses and dissertations which contain embedded PJAs as part of the formal submission can be posted publicly by the awarding institution with DOI links back to the formal publications on ScienceDirect.

If you are affiliated with a library that subscribes to ScienceDirect you have additional private sharing rights for others' research accessed under that agreement. This includes use for classroom teaching and internal training at the institution (including use in course packs and courseware programs), and inclusion of the article for grant funding purposes.

Gold Open Access Articles: May be shared according to the author-selected end-user license and should contain a [CrossMark logo](#), the end user license, and a DOI link to the formal publication on ScienceDirect.

Please refer to Elsevier's [posting policy](#) for further information.

18. **For book authors** the following clauses are applicable in addition to the above: Authors are permitted to place a brief summary of their work online only. You are not allowed to download and post the published electronic version of your chapter, nor may you scan the printed edition to create an electronic version. **Posting to a repository:** Authors are permitted to post a summary of their chapter only in their institution's repository.

19. **Thesis/Dissertation:** If your license is for use in a thesis/dissertation your thesis may be submitted to your institution in either print or electronic form. Should your thesis be published commercially, please reapply for permission. These requirements include permission for the Library and Archives of Canada to supply single copies, on demand, of the complete thesis and include permission for Proquest/UMI to supply single copies, on demand, of the complete thesis. Should your thesis be published commercially, please reapply for permission. Theses and dissertations which contain embedded PJAs as part of the formal submission can be posted publicly by the awarding institution with DOI links back to the formal publications on ScienceDirect.

Elsevier Open Access Terms and Conditions

You can publish open access with Elsevier in hundreds of open access journals or in nearly 2000 established subscription journals that support open access publishing. Permitted third party re-use of these open access articles is defined by the author's choice of Creative Commons user license. See our [open access license policy](#) for more information.

Terms & Conditions applicable to all Open Access articles published with Elsevier:

Any reuse of the article must not represent the author as endorsing the adaptation of the article nor should the article be modified in such a way as to damage the author's honour or reputation. If any changes have been made, such changes must be clearly indicated.

The author(s) must be appropriately credited and we ask that you include the end user license and a DOI link to the formal publication on ScienceDirect.

If any part of the material to be used (for example, figures) has appeared in our publication with credit or acknowledgement to another source it is the responsibility of the user to ensure their reuse complies with the terms and conditions determined by the rights holder.

Additional Terms & Conditions applicable to each Creative Commons user license:

CC BY: The CC-BY license allows users to copy, to create extracts, abstracts and new works from the Article, to alter and revise the Article and to make commercial use of the Article (including reuse and/or resale of the Article by commercial entities), provided the user gives appropriate credit (with a link to the formal publication through the relevant DOI), provides a link to the license, indicates if changes were made and the licensor is not represented as endorsing the use made of the work. The full details of the license are available at <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>.

CC BY NC SA: The CC BY-NC-SA license allows users to copy, to create extracts, abstracts and new works from the Article, to alter and revise the Article, provided this is not done for commercial purposes, and that the user gives appropriate credit (with a link to the formal publication through the relevant DOI), provides a link to the license, indicates if changes were made and the licensor is not represented as endorsing the use made of the work. Further, any new works must be made available on the same conditions. The full details of the license are available at <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/4.0>.

CC BY NC ND: The CC BY-NC-ND license allows users to copy and distribute the Article, provided this is not done for commercial purposes and further does not permit distribution of the Article if it is changed or edited in any way, and provided the user gives appropriate credit (with a link to the formal publication through the relevant DOI), provides a link to the license, and that the licensor is not represented as endorsing the use made of the work. The full details of the license are available at <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-nd/4.0>. Any commercial reuse of Open Access articles published with a CC BY NC SA or CC BY NC ND license requires permission from Elsevier and will be subject to a fee.

Commercial reuse includes:

- Associating advertising with the full text of the Article
- Charging fees for document delivery or access
- Article aggregation
- Systematic distribution via e-mail lists or share buttons

Posting or linking by commercial companies for use by customers of those companies.

20. Other Conditions:

v1.10

Questions? customercare@copyright.com or +1-855-239-3415 (toll free in the US) or +1-978-646-2777.

JOHN WILEY AND SONS LICENSE
TERMS AND CONDITIONS

Nov 08, 2020

This Agreement between Mr. Achmed Mrestani ("You") and John Wiley and Sons ("John Wiley and Sons") consists of your license details and the terms and conditions provided by John Wiley and Sons and Copyright Clearance Center.

License Number 4944200199345

License date Nov 08, 2020

Licensed Content Publisher John Wiley and Sons

Licensed Content Publication Angewandte Chemie International Edition

Licensed Content Title Subdiffraction-Resolution Fluorescence Imaging with Conventional Fluorescent Probes

Licensed Content Author Mike Heilemann, Sebastian van de Linde, Mark Schüttpelz, et al

Licensed Content Date Jul 29, 2008

Licensed Content Volume 47

Licensed Content Issue 33

Licensed Content Pages 5

Type of use Dissertation/Thesis

Requestor type University/Academic

Format	Print and electronic
Portion	Figure/table
Number of figures/tables	1
Will you be translating?	No
Title	Strukturelle Differenzierung und Plastizität präsynaptischer Aktiver Zonen
Institution name	University of Würzburg
Expected presentation date	Jan 2021
Order reference number	heilemann2008
Portions	Figure 1
Requestor Location	Mr. Achmed Mrestani Geiststraße 23 Halle, Sachsen-Anhalt 06108 Germany Attn: Mr. Achmed Mrestani
Publisher Tax ID	EU826007151
Total	0.00 EUR
Terms and Conditions	

TERMS AND CONDITIONS

This copyrighted material is owned by or exclusively licensed to John Wiley & Sons, Inc. or one of its group companies (each a "Wiley Company") or handled on behalf of a society with which a Wiley Company has exclusive publishing rights in relation to a particular work (collectively "WILEY"). By clicking "accept" in connection with completing this licensing transaction, you agree that the following terms and conditions apply to this transaction (along with the billing and payment terms and conditions established by the Copyright Clearance Center Inc., ("CCC's Billing and Payment terms and conditions"), at the time that

you opened your RightsLink account (these are available at any time at <http://myaccount.copyright.com>).

Terms and Conditions

- The materials you have requested permission to reproduce or reuse (the "Wiley Materials") are protected by copyright.
- You are hereby granted a personal, non-exclusive, non-sub licensable (on a stand-alone basis), non-transferable, worldwide, limited license to reproduce the Wiley Materials for the purpose specified in the licensing process. This license, **and any CONTENT (PDF or image file) purchased as part of your order**, is for a one-time use only and limited to any maximum distribution number specified in the license. The first instance of republication or reuse granted by this license must be completed within two years of the date of the grant of this license (although copies prepared before the end date may be distributed thereafter). The Wiley Materials shall not be used in any other manner or for any other purpose, beyond what is granted in the license. Permission is granted subject to an appropriate acknowledgement given to the author, title of the material/book/journal and the publisher. You shall also duplicate the copyright notice that appears in the Wiley publication in your use of the Wiley Material. Permission is also granted on the understanding that nowhere in the text is a previously published source acknowledged for all or part of this Wiley Material. Any third party content is expressly excluded from this permission.
- With respect to the Wiley Materials, all rights are reserved. Except as expressly granted by the terms of the license, no part of the Wiley Materials may be copied, modified, adapted (except for minor reformatting required by the new Publication), translated, reproduced, transferred or distributed, in any form or by any means, and no derivative works may be made based on the Wiley Materials without the prior permission of the respective copyright owner. **For STM Signatory Publishers clearing permission under the terms of the [STM Permissions Guidelines](#) only, the terms of the license are extended to include subsequent editions and for editions in other languages, provided such editions are for the work as a whole in situ and does not involve the separate exploitation of the permitted figures or extracts**, You may not alter, remove or suppress in any manner any copyright, trademark or other notices displayed by the Wiley Materials. You may not license, rent, sell, loan, lease, pledge, offer as security, transfer or assign the Wiley Materials on a stand-alone basis, or any of the rights granted to you hereunder to any other person.
- The Wiley Materials and all of the intellectual property rights therein shall at all times remain the exclusive property of John Wiley & Sons Inc, the Wiley Companies, or their respective licensors, and your interest therein is only that of having possession of and the right to reproduce the Wiley Materials pursuant to Section 2 herein during the continuance of this Agreement. You agree that you own no right, title or interest in or to the Wiley Materials or any of the intellectual property rights therein. You shall have no rights hereunder other than the license as provided for above in Section 2. No right, license or interest to any trademark, trade name, service mark or other branding ("Marks") of WILEY or its licensors is granted hereunder, and you agree that you shall not assert any such right, license or interest with respect thereto
- NEITHER WILEY NOR ITS LICENSORS MAKES ANY WARRANTY OR REPRESENTATION OF ANY KIND TO YOU OR ANY THIRD PARTY, EXPRESS, IMPLIED OR STATUTORY, WITH RESPECT TO THE MATERIALS OR THE ACCURACY OF ANY INFORMATION CONTAINED IN THE

MATERIALS, INCLUDING, WITHOUT LIMITATION, ANY IMPLIED WARRANTY OF MERCHANTABILITY, ACCURACY, SATISFACTORY QUALITY, FITNESS FOR A PARTICULAR PURPOSE, USABILITY, INTEGRATION OR NON-INFRINGEMENT AND ALL SUCH WARRANTIES ARE HEREBY EXCLUDED BY WILEY AND ITS LICENSORS AND WAIVED BY YOU.

- WILEY shall have the right to terminate this Agreement immediately upon breach of this Agreement by you.
- You shall indemnify, defend and hold harmless WILEY, its Licensors and their respective directors, officers, agents and employees, from and against any actual or threatened claims, demands, causes of action or proceedings arising from any breach of this Agreement by you.
- IN NO EVENT SHALL WILEY OR ITS LICENSORS BE LIABLE TO YOU OR ANY OTHER PARTY OR ANY OTHER PERSON OR ENTITY FOR ANY SPECIAL, CONSEQUENTIAL, INCIDENTAL, INDIRECT, EXEMPLARY OR PUNITIVE DAMAGES, HOWEVER CAUSED, ARISING OUT OF OR IN CONNECTION WITH THE DOWNLOADING, PROVISIONING, VIEWING OR USE OF THE MATERIALS REGARDLESS OF THE FORM OF ACTION, WHETHER FOR BREACH OF CONTRACT, BREACH OF WARRANTY, TORT, NEGLIGENCE, INFRINGEMENT OR OTHERWISE (INCLUDING, WITHOUT LIMITATION, DAMAGES BASED ON LOSS OF PROFITS, DATA, FILES, USE, BUSINESS OPPORTUNITY OR CLAIMS OF THIRD PARTIES), AND WHETHER OR NOT THE PARTY HAS BEEN ADVISED OF THE POSSIBILITY OF SUCH DAMAGES. THIS LIMITATION SHALL APPLY NOTWITHSTANDING ANY FAILURE OF ESSENTIAL PURPOSE OF ANY LIMITED REMEDY PROVIDED HEREIN.
- Should any provision of this Agreement be held by a court of competent jurisdiction to be illegal, invalid, or unenforceable, that provision shall be deemed amended to achieve as nearly as possible the same economic effect as the original provision, and the legality, validity and enforceability of the remaining provisions of this Agreement shall not be affected or impaired thereby.
- The failure of either party to enforce any term or condition of this Agreement shall not constitute a waiver of either party's right to enforce each and every term and condition of this Agreement. No breach under this agreement shall be deemed waived or excused by either party unless such waiver or consent is in writing signed by the party granting such waiver or consent. The waiver by or consent of a party to a breach of any provision of this Agreement shall not operate or be construed as a waiver of or consent to any other or subsequent breach by such other party.
- This Agreement may not be assigned (including by operation of law or otherwise) by you without WILEY's prior written consent.
- Any fee required for this permission shall be non-refundable after thirty (30) days from receipt by the CCC.
- These terms and conditions together with CCC's Billing and Payment terms and conditions (which are incorporated herein) form the entire agreement between you and WILEY concerning this licensing transaction and (in the absence of fraud) supersedes all prior agreements and representations of the parties, oral or written. This Agreement

may not be amended except in writing signed by both parties. This Agreement shall be binding upon and inure to the benefit of the parties' successors, legal representatives, and authorized assigns.

- In the event of any conflict between your obligations established by these terms and conditions and those established by CCC's Billing and Payment terms and conditions, these terms and conditions shall prevail.
- WILEY expressly reserves all rights not specifically granted in the combination of (i) the license details provided by you and accepted in the course of this licensing transaction, (ii) these terms and conditions and (iii) CCC's Billing and Payment terms and conditions.
- This Agreement will be void if the Type of Use, Format, Circulation, or Requestor Type was misrepresented during the licensing process.
- This Agreement shall be governed by and construed in accordance with the laws of the State of New York, USA, without regards to such state's conflict of law rules. Any legal action, suit or proceeding arising out of or relating to these Terms and Conditions or the breach thereof shall be instituted in a court of competent jurisdiction in New York County in the State of New York in the United States of America and each party hereby consents and submits to the personal jurisdiction of such court, waives any objection to venue in such court and consents to service of process by registered or certified mail, return receipt requested, at the last known address of such party.

WILEY OPEN ACCESS TERMS AND CONDITIONS

Wiley Publishes Open Access Articles in fully Open Access Journals and in Subscription journals offering Online Open. Although most of the fully Open Access journals publish open access articles under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) License only, the subscription journals and a few of the Open Access Journals offer a choice of Creative Commons Licenses. The license type is clearly identified on the article.

The Creative Commons Attribution License

The [Creative Commons Attribution License \(CC-BY\)](#) allows users to copy, distribute and transmit an article, adapt the article and make commercial use of the article. The CC-BY license permits commercial and non-

Creative Commons Attribution Non-Commercial License

The [Creative Commons Attribution Non-Commercial \(CC-BY-NC\) License](#) permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited and is not used for commercial purposes.(see below)

Creative Commons Attribution-Non-Commercial-NoDerivs License

The [Creative Commons Attribution Non-Commercial-NoDerivs License](#) (CC-BY-NC-ND) permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited, is not used for commercial purposes and no modifications or adaptations are made. (see below)

Use by commercial "for-profit" organizations

Use of Wiley Open Access articles for commercial, promotional, or marketing purposes requires further explicit permission from Wiley and will be subject to a fee.

Further details can be found on Wiley Online Library <http://olabout.wiley.com/WileyCDA/Section/id-410895.html>

Other Terms and Conditions:

v1.10 Last updated September 2015

Questions? customercare@copyright.com or +1-855-239-3415 (toll free in the US) or +1-978-646-2777.

RE: permission for reuse in a medical doctoral thesis

Wiley Global Permissions <permissions@wiley.com>

Mo, 09.11.2020 17:54

An: Achmed Mrestani <Achmed-Mrestani@hotmail.de>

Dear Achmed,

Thank you for your email.

Permission is hereby granted for the use requested subject to the usual acknowledgements (author, title of material, title of journal, ourselves as publisher). You should also duplicate the copyright notice that appears in the Wiley publication; this can be found on the copyright page in the journal.

Any third party material is expressly excluded from this permission. If any of the material you wish to use appears within our work with credit to another source, authorization from that source must be obtained.

This permission does not include the right to grant others permission to photocopy or otherwise reproduce this material except for accessible versions made by non-profit organizations serving the blind, visually impaired and other persons with print disabilities (VIPs).

Sincerely,

[Sheik Safdar](#)

Sales Specialist – Permissions

Global Sales Partnerships

Wileyssafdar@wiley.com

T +1 201-748-6512

111 River Street
Hoboken, NJ 07030-5774
U.S.

permissions@wiley.com**WILEY**

From: Achmed Mrestani <Achmed-Mrestani@hotmail.de>**Sent:** Sunday, November 8, 2020 7:38 AM**To:** Wiley Global Permissions <permissions@wiley.com>**Subject:** permission for reuse in a medical doctoral thesis**This is an external email.**

Dear ladies and gentleman,

I try to obtain the permission to reuse a Figure for my medical doctoral thesis from the journal 'Current Protocols in Molecular Biology' (doi.: 10.1002/0471142727.mb3102s111) . The link to Copyright Clearance Center RightsLink forwarded me directly to you, since the the content of a data filed value is preventing RightsLink to finish the request. Can you help me to obtain the license for reuse?

I am looking forward to your answer.

Best regards,
Achmed Mrestani

Virenfrei. www.avast.com